

AN EXAMINATION OF SU FI (ISLAMIC MYSTICAL) PRACTICES WITHIN THE CONTEXT OF QUR'AN AND SUNNAH

By

AYINDE SHEHU JAWONDO

*Department of Arabic Medium, School of
Junior Secondary Education,
Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin.*

Abstract

Sufism (Tasawwuf) was designed towards the actualization of the goal set by Islam. It is a well-known fact that many of the most eminent defenders of Islamic orthodoxy, such as 'Abd al-Qadir Jilani, Salah ad-Din and Al-Ghazali were Sufis. Notwithstanding, as some scholars see Sufism as the heart of Islam, others consider it heretical or unislamic. This paper, therefore, examines some of the major practices of the Sufis and tries to see whether or not they are in conformity or agreement with the context of Qur'an and Sunnah. Only five Sufi practices were examined and proven with quotations from both the Qur'an and Sunnah and it was discovered that though there may be extremists among the adherents of Sufism, Sufi practices are mainly Islamic.

Keywords: *Sufi, Quran and Sunnah*

Introduction

Sufism in its entirety is not a religion but a way of actualizing the main goal of Islam which is to gain God's pleasure. Sirhindi in Ansari (1986) says:

The sufi tariqah is only a means to achieve the realities of religious life as defined by shari'ah. It is only to confirm what the shari'ah says, and not to tell anything new or add any new dimension. There are no realities outside the shari'ah and the sufi tariqah is only a further help to attain those realities (p. 75).

Seeking the knowledge about God, sincere worship and devotion, purification of soul from its dirt which include envy, hatred, materialism, wickedness, rudeness, arrogance, pride, selfishness etc., meditation and Dhikr (remembrance of God) to mention but a few are the major preoccupations of the Sufis.

A school of thought believes that Sufism is the heart of Islam and that it is a way of ensuring rapid religious or spiritual advancement most especially in the periods after prophet Muhammad (S.A.W), Another school of thought holds the view that Sufism is foreign to Islam and that all its practices are heretical. (Ansari, 1986, p.7). Based on the these divergent opinions about Sufism, this paper looks into the meaning of Sufism, its goals as well as its origin and development in Islam. It also examines the position of Shari'ah vis-à-vis Sufi practices.

Origin of the word "Sufism"

There are diverse opinions on the origin of the word "Sufism". To some, "Sufism" is from Arabic word "safa" which means purity, Al-Jilani in Tosun (1992) submits:

The name sufi is an expression derived from the Arabic word "saf", "Pure". The reason that the sufis are called by this name is that their inner world is purified and enlightened with the light of wisdom, unity and oneness. (p.40).

Others say that Sufism is traceable to the people of the bench during the time of the prophet (i.e. Muhammad). This is evident in Valiuddin's (1978) submission:

They were called sufis because their qualities resembled those of the people of the Bench (Ashab al-suffa) who lived in the time of God's prophet. They had left this world, departed from their homes and fled from their companions. They took of this world's good only so much as

was indispensable for covering the nakedness and allaying hunger (p.2).

In addition, some assert that the Sufis are so called because of their habit of wearing woolen garments known in Arabic as "Sufi", while others opine that it is because they are in the first rank (Saff-I-Awwal) before God through their turning of their hearts towards Him. Some scholars, most especially, the westerners trace the origin of the word "Sufism" to a Greek word "Sophia" which means wisdom. (Annemarie, 1975, p.14).

In modern times, Sufis are only known not by wearing woolen garments nor by outward renunciation of this world, but by their extraordinary purity in soul and character and by their ever-flowing wisdom. By implication, tracing the origin of the word Sufism" to "purity" and "wisdom" is more appropriate, more reasonable and more relevant to the present time.

What is Sufism?

Sufism is the generally accepted name for Islamic mysticism. It is a broad term which has been defined in multifarious ways by different people among whom are the Sufis themselves, non-sufis and non-muslims as well. Their views on this concept, according to Annemarie (1975), are:

Like the blind men in Rumi's famous story, when they were made to touch an elephant each described it according to the part of the body his hands had touched: to one, the elephant appeared like a throne, to another like a fan, or like a water pipe, or like a pillar; But none was able to imagine what the whole animal would look like. Such is the case with Sufis. (p.3).

Notwithstanding, some definitions of Sufism are given below: Sufism, according to Richard (1982), is "a search for God" (p.54). It is also seen by

David (1996) as "turning away of the heart from things to the Lord of things" (p.138). Abu'l Hasan Nuri in Mir Valiuddin (1978) defines Sufism as "the renunciation of all selfish pleasures" (p.4). Reynold (1979) briefly defines Sufism "as self-discipline". (p.26). Junaid (d. 297/909) in Ansari (1986) says that Sufism is "that your devotion to God is not for any other purpose" (p.31); while Tustari says: "It is to eat little, to seek peace in God and to flee from people (Ansari, 1986, p.31).

Having critically examined the above definitions, it can be noticed that the common variables in all the definitions are God and this world. He therefore sees Sufism as the act of seeking God through renunciation of worldly things.

Origin and Development of Sufism in Islam

There are controversies regarding whether or not Sufism is Islamic. Some see it as the heart of Islam without which no individual can perfect his religion while others see it as completely alien to Islam. (Ansari, 1986, pp. 61-62). Each group explains this based on its perspectives. Those who support are of the view that all the Sufi practice of devotion, solitude, meditation, remembrance of God, God's love etc are nothing but the real messages which the prophet of Islam had come to deliver. However, the other group views Sufism not through its practice but its name. To this category, the word "Sufism or Sufi" in its Arabic form is not found in the Qur'an and Hadith which are the two major sources of Islamic law (Shari'ah). (Matheson, 1976, pp. 16-17).

It is therefore worthy of note that Sufism in practice originated from the time of the prophet although, there was no special name given to it. Nasr, quoted by Richard (1982) submits: "The name "Sufi" did not exist in the time of the prophet, but the reality did (p.54). The name "Sufi", according to Qushayri in Valihuddin (1978), came into vogue a little before the expiry of

the second century Hijri (or 822 C.E.) (p.3):

During the golden time of the prophet, all the so-called sufi practices were fully embodied in the practice of Islam. Sincere devotion to God's worship, solitude for the remembrance of God, meditation on the signs or creatures of God, seeking God at all times, renunciation of worldly things and a host of others were common practices among the companions and other muslims. The presence of the prophet was indeed a blessing to the people of his time. He used to put them right when they were wrong and give them necessary advice when the need arose. The companions of the prophet, after his departure, were able to keep Islam in a high spirit as laid down by the prophet; nothing was added nor subtracted. The followers of the companions popularly known as Tabi'un equally upheld the spirit after their predecessors.

When the high spirit in the practice of Islam started to diminish towards the tail end of the second century of Hijrah, what is now termed "Sufism" or "Tasawwuf" sprang up to correct the situation and bring back the lost appetite for Islam. (Mir Valiuddin, 1978, p.3).

It was from this generation that "Sufism" was passed on to people of different generations in unbroken succession until the present age.

What is Shari'ah?

Shari'ah, as defined by Sirhindi in Ansari (1986), is "the rules and regulations of the Qur'an and the Sunnah concerning worship and rites, morals and society, economy and government" (p.71). Also, Schacht in Richard (1982, p.48) sees it as: "the totality of God's commands that regulate the life of every muslim in all its aspects".

Shari'ah covers all aspects of human life- be it social, political, economic, religious or otherwise. It is drawn from Al-Qur'an (God's words), Hadith (prophetic traditions), Qiyas (analogy) and Ijma' (consensus). It must therefore be emphasized that the first two sources (i.e. Qur'an and Hadith)

are inevitable and fundamental. Therefore, any issue in Islam whose reference cannot be drawn from these two main sources is always considered heretical.

Sufi Practices in the Context of Qur'an and Sunnah

Here, an attempt is made to examine some sufi practices and see their agreement or otherwise with the Qur'an and Sunnah. It must be borne in mind that sufi practices are very numerous but some among those that are major, fundamental and basic shall be dealt with. This may become necessary if one considers the fact that the focus of both the Shari'ah and that of Sufism are identical.

Focus of the Sufis

Although, there are numerous Sufi orders like Qadiriyyah, Rifa'iyyah, Sanusiyyah, Tijaniyyah and a host of others but their chief aim or goal is one and that is purification of soul for the realization of the truth (i.e. God). Richard (1982, p. 55) submits, "Though the roads are various, the goal is one. So, if you consider the roads, the variety is great and the divergence infinite; but when you consider the goal, they are all of one accord."

According to Valiuddin (1978), "its subject matter is the purification of the soul and its end or aim is the attainment of eternal felicity and blessedness". Javad (1979) also asserts: "the aim of Sufism is the realization of the Truth."

In the Shari'ah, realization of God is equally supreme. All forms of worship are tailored towards reaching Him. Qur'an 5 verse 35 reads. "O you who believe, do your duty to Allah, seek the means of approach unto Him, and strive with might in His cause so that you may be successful." Also, Q.51, v.56 says, "I have only created Jinns and men that they may serve Me." These portions show that only God should be the target of all creations. In the final

analysis, it can be stated that the focus or goal of both the Shari'ah and Sufism is similar, i.e. realization of God.

Sufis' Means to Achieving their Goals

In order to achieve their major goal, which is the realization of God (or the Truth), the Sufis have laid down some practices among which are the following: Purification of soul, God's remembrance, meditation, solitude etc. Each of these practices shall be looked into within the content of Shari'ah.

Purification of the Soul

According to the Sufis, no meaningful spiritual advancement can be achieved until the heart is cleaned and all forms of dirt such as love of the world, hatred, greed, envy, enmity, etc. are purged out of it and replaced with worthwhile virtues. (Nasim, 1994, pp. 7-8).

Hence, to purify their souls, the Sufis engage in serious prayer, Dhikr (remembrance of God) and constant practice of removing all negative thoughts from their hearts and replacing them with positive ones. Jilani in Tosun (1992) says: "purification for the purpose of attaining the divine essence is through continuous remembrance and the invocation of the confession of unity." (p.76). This practice is justified by Q: 87, V:14 which reads. "Indeed whosoever purifies himself (his soul) shall achieve success." Moreover, there are so many verses of the Qur'an which lay much emphasis on the purification of soul. These include: "Truly, he succeeds who purifies it (his soul) and he fails who corrupts it" (Q. 91 VV. 9-10). "But those will prosper, who purify themselves" (Q.87, V.14). The prophet was quoted to have said: "*lo! there is a piece of flesh in human body. If it is reformed and purified the whole body is reformed and purified and when this piece is corrupted the whole body is corrupted; remember that this piece of flesh is your heart!*" (Musa, 1973, p. 29).

From the above quotations, it is quite clear that the practice of

purifying one's soul as engaged in by the Sufis takes its root from both the Qur'an and Hadith of the prophet. Added to that, one of the means of purifying one's soul is by dhikr.

Dhikr

Dhikr simply means remembrance of God. It is also seen as "all repetitive recitation of sacred formulas or sacred speech, whether it be aloud or inward" (Matheson, 1976, p.100). In the perspective of the Sufis, Dhikr is seen as the total and uncompromised attention to God; ignoring all that is not God (Javad, 1989, p.32). It is an instrument of clearing the heart's dirt and moving closer to God. Al-Ghazzal in Charis (1976), while talking on the purification of the hearts, says "... and the means of clearing it is dhikr Allah, i.e. commemoration of God and concentration of every thought upon Him. (p.166). Also, Muhtar (1981) submits: "the shortest route by which to draw nearer to God is remembrance, dhikr". (p.67).

Two main types of Dhikr are always embarked upon by the sufis; the vocal (Jaliy) and the silent or Dhikr of the heart (khafiy). The former is always said aloud either by individuals or in sufi gatherings while the latter does not involve opening of mouth or uttering of words but is done secretly in the heart. (Javad, 1989, p.34).

Dhikr is encouraged in the holy Qur'an (see-Q 29, v 45; Q 2 v 152; Q33 v 41 and Q13:v. 28) and the prophet also says: "the example of the one who remembers Allah in comparison to the one who does not remember his Lord, is that of a living creature compared to a dead one". (Is'haq, 1997, pp. 124-125) and "No human being has done any deed more likely to save him from Allah's punishment than the remembrance of Allah." (Al-Hafiz, 2002, p. 485). It was also narrated by Abu Hurayrah that the prophet stated: Allah observed: I am with My slave when he remembers Me and moves his lips with remembrance.(Syed, 1996, p.64).

From the above Quranic and prophetic quotations, it is quite clear that Dhikr (remembrance of God) is a way of cleansing the hearts of dirt and a means of drawing closer to God. Hence, the practice of Dhikr by the Sufis can be accepted as being in line with the teaching of Islam.

Meditation

According to the Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary, to mediate on something is to think deeply usually in silence, especially for religious purposes or in order to relax (p. 728). Lobsang R. (1977) submits:

Meditation is a special form of concentration or directed thinking which disciplines the mind, and which forms a special attitude of mind; meditation is that form of directed thought which enables us to perceive through the subconscious and other systems that which would not be possible for us to perceive in any other way (p. 149).

Meditation is a core and inevitable practice in Sufism. Emphasis is always placed by the Sufis on constant meditation for spiritual progress. The creation of heaven and earth, the natural phenomena, human creation, animals, this world and the life after death, paradise and hell fire, etc. are their objects of meditation. (Matheson, 1976, p.106).

Many verses of the Qur'an enjoin the practice of meditation. Q 16:v.44 says "we sent down to you this scripture that you might clarify to the people whatever descends to them so that they might reflect". "There are those who remember God standing and sitting and reclining and who reflect upon the creation of heaven and earth" (Q3:V191). "Thus, we explain fully the signs for those who reflect." (Q10:V 24). Considering the above facts, it is clear that meditation as being observed by the Sufis is supported by Qur'anic verses. Sequel to that, the practice is Islamic.

Solitude

Solitude is the state or situation of being alone without companions. Among the Sufis, solitude is a practice of staying alone in a separate and silent place in the city or wilderness in order to avoid worldly distractions for the purpose of worship, seeking closeness to God and spiritual advancement (Tosun, 1992, p.93). To them, the world is too busy so much so that no one who devotes himself to worldly activities can ever record any meaningful spiritual progress. For this only reason, they try to use some parts of their time in solitude. The sufis inherited this practice from prophet Muhammed (SAW) who used to be in solitude. Muhammed Haykal (1982) narrates:

At the head of Mount Hira: two miles north of Makkah, Muhammad discovered a cave whose perfect silence and total separation from Makkah made of it a perfect place for retreat. In that cave Muhammad used to spend the whole month of Ramadan. He would satisfy himself with the least provisions, carried to him from time to time by a servant, while devoting himself uninterruptedly to his spiritual pursuits in peace, solitude and tranquility. His devotion often caused him to forget himself, to forget his food and, indeed to forget the whole world around him. (p.70)

Moreover, Umar, the second Khalifah of the prophet said "have your share of solitude". Ibn 'Abbas, one of the companions of the prophet also submitted: "the best of all sittings is that observed in a corner of your room where you see nothing and you are not seen" (Muhammad Al-Ghazzali, 1997, V. 2.pp 192-193).

From the above submissions, it is quite indisputable that solitude is a practice welcomed and encouraged by Islam.

Conclusion

Having examined the major practices of the sufis which include the aim of realizing God, purification of soul, remembrance of God (Dhikr), meditation and solitude, and having established their compatibility or concord with the Qur'an and Sunnah, it can be concluded that Sufi practices are Islamic. This is so because they are traceable to the prophet and his companions. Even if any anomaly is noticed about anybody claiming to be Sufi, this should not be used as a yardstick to measure Sufism as a whole or to determine its standard in the same way Islam, as a religion, could not be judged based on the characters of some faithless or ill-behaved Muslims. An individual must be judged by his or her religion and not vice versa. Shari'ah is therefore the root from which the stem of Sufism emanated.

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